

Chemistry of the Constituents of *Putranjiva roxburghii*

PASUPATI SENGUPTA*, SHYAMAL K. GHOSH and SAKTIPADA DAS

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 22 September 1995

Chemical investigations of different parts of *Putranjiva roxburghii* Wall. (Syn. *Drypetes roxburghii* Wall.), a common Indian medicinal plant^{1,2} of the Euphorbiaceae family, have so far yielded eight known and seventeen new compounds³ that are listed in Table 1. Although a large amount of work has been done on the chemistry of these seventeen new compounds, the present review is restricted only to the work done in our laboratory on the structure elucidation and transformations of seven new compounds isolated from the said plant. All these compounds studied by us are derivatives of D:A-friedooleanane and 3,4-*seco*-D:A-friedooleanane.

TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS ISOLATED FROM *Putranjiva roxburghii* WALL.

Plant part	Compounds isolated	Ref.
Barks	Friedelin ^a , friedelanol (6) ^a , putranjivadiene (1), roxburgholone (10) and putranjic acid (putric acid) (12)	4–12
Leaves	β -Amyrin ^a , β -amyrin palmitate ^a , stigmasterol ^a , putrone (21), putrol (22), putranjivic acid (11), roxburghonic acid (30), putraflavone, amentoflavone ^a , 4'''- <i>O</i> -methylamentoflavone ^a , 4'''',7-di- <i>O</i> -methylamentoflavone ^a and putranjiva saponins-A,B,C,D	10, 13–17
Seed-coats	Putranjivoside and putranosides-A,B,C,D	18–21

^aPreviously known compounds.

Putranjivadiene (1)⁴

Putranjivadiene (1), C₃₀H₄₈O₂, isolated from the trunk bark^{4,11} and root bark⁷ has two ketonic groups, one of them being hindered. The basic skeleton of this diketone was established by its reduction to the monoketone (2) by Huang-Minlon reduction and finally to friedelane (3) by forced Wolff-Kishner reduction of 2. On reduction with LiAlH₄, putranjivadiene furnished putranjivadiol (4) but on reduction with NaBH₄ the monohydroxy ketone (5) was obtained. On forced Wolff-Kishner reduction the latter yielded friedelanol (6), thus establishing that one of the carbonyl groups is present at C-3 in 1. Considering the

pmr spectra of the above compounds, the position of the other carbonyl group was shown to be at C-7.

The monoketone (2) on reduction with LiAlH₄ gave the alcohol (7) which could not be acetylated due to severe 1,3-diaxial interactions with the axial methyl groups at C-5, C-9 and C-14 but could be smoothly dehydrated to the olefin (8). On the other hand, reduction of 2 with sodium in amyl alcohol afforded the hydroxy compound (9) which underwent easy acetylation. Thus the hydroxyl group in 7 is obviously axial and that in 9 equatorial. A detailed study of the mass spectral fragmentations of these compounds (1-9) then established the complete structure of putranjivadiene as D:A-friedoolean-3,7-dione (1).

Roxburgholone (10)⁵

Roxburgholone (10), C₃₀H₅₀O₂, obtained from the stem bark^{5,11} and root bark⁷ of *P. roxburghii* has a hydroxyl group and a ketonic function and on oxidation it furnished putranjivadiene (1). However, 10 was not identical with 5 obtained from NaBH₄ reduction of 1, indicating that these two hydroxy ketones are epimers. Reduction of roxburgholone with LiAlH₄ followed by acetylation and dehydration of the acetate yielded an ene-acetate and comparison of these compounds with those obtained from 1 under identical conditions established the structure of roxburgholone as 3 α -hydroxy-D:A-friedoolean-7-one (10).

Putranjic acid (11)²⁴ and putranjivic acid (12)²⁴

From the trunk bark and root bark of the plant, Garg and Mitra^{11,12} and Seshadri *et al.*⁷⁻⁹ isolated putranjic (putric) acid, C₃₀H₅₂O₃, for which both groups of workers independently suggested the 4,5-*seco*-friedelane (11) structure on the basis of spectral data and chemical transformations. From the leaves, Seshadri *et al.*^{9,10} isolated another acid, named putranjivic acid, C₃₀H₅₀O₂, and suggested its structure as 12. These authors also correlated these two acids with each other by transformations but these acids were not correlated with any compound of known structure and stereochemistry. We ultimately confirmed²⁴ these structures by synthesis of methyl putranjivate (13) from friedel-3-ene (14). From a study of the circular dichroism curve of the xanthate ester (15) of putranjic acid (11) that showed a positive Cotton effect around 360 m μ , 11 was shown to contain *S*-configuration at C-2. Thus putranjic acid and putranjivic acid were assigned the structures 2*S*-hydroxy-

*Present address : B-10/249, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal.

3,4-*seco*-D:A-friedoolean-3-oic acid (11) and 3,4-*seco*-D:A-friedoolean-4(23)-en-3-oic acid (12) respectively.

- 1, $R^1=R^2=O$
- 2, $R^1=H_2, R^2=O$
- 3, $R^1=R^2=H_2$
- 4, $R^1=\alpha-H, \beta-OH,$
 $R^2=\alpha-H, \beta-OH$
- 5, $R^1=\alpha-H, \beta-OH, R^2=O$
- 6, $R^1=\alpha-H, \beta-OH, R^2=H_2$
- 7, $R^1=H_2; R^2=\alpha-H, \beta-OH$
- 9, $R^1=H_2, R^2=\alpha-OH, \beta-H$
- 10, $R^1=\beta-H, \alpha-OH, R^2=O$
- 17, $R^1=\beta-OAc, \alpha-H,$
 $R^2=\beta-OH, \alpha-H$

- 11, $R^1=COOH, R^2=OH$
15, $R^1=COOMe; R^2=C S. SMe$

Chart 1

Functionalisation of 25-methyl group of D:A-friedooleananes²⁵

After the structure of putranjivadiene (1) was settled, we believed it to be the suitable substrate for introducing oxygen functions at the C-25 methyl group. The axial 7β -hydroxy group in both 4 and 7 suffers from severe 1,3-diaxial interaction by three methyl groups at C-5, C-9 and C-13 and hence we predicted that hypohalite oxidation might effect functionalisation of any or all the three methyl groups. Irradiation of a mixture of 7, lead tetraacetate, iodine and calcium carbonate in cyclohexane for 3.5 h with a 500 W tungsten lamp afforded 7β , 25-oxido-D:A-friedooleanane (16) with little amount of friedelane (3). Similar treatment of the 3β -acetoxy derivative (17) of 4 afforded 3β -acetoxy- 7β , 25-oxido-D:A-friedooleanane (18) as the major product. Both 16 and 18 on mild treatment with $BF_3 \cdot Et_2O$ in acetic anhydride furnished the ene-acetates 19 and 20 respectively. The above functionalised products were then subsequently used by us^{22,26-28} for structure elucidation of

some other compounds isolated from *P. roxburghii* by other groups of workers.

Putrone (21)^{22,26} and putrol (22)^{22,23}

From the leaves of *P. roxburghii*, Seshadri *et al.*¹⁷ isolated two closely related 25-nor-triterpenes putrone and putrol and suggested the structure of putrone as 3-oxo-25-nor-friedel-9(11)-ene (21) mainly on the basis of mass spectral fragmentation patterns. Since putrol was obtained by reduction of 21 with $NaBH_4$, the structure of putrol was proposed as 3 α -hydroxy-25-nor-friedel-9(11)-ene (23). These two compounds were however not correlated with any known compound. We confirmed these proposed structures by correlation of these two compounds with putranjivadiene (1) as stated below.

Putrone (21) on Huang-Minlon reduction afforded 24 which on oxidation with SeO_2 in acetic acid yielded the diene (25). We treated the ene-acetate (19) with $LiAlH_4$ to get the alcohol (26) which on boiling with $Pb(OAc)_4$, and $Cu(OAc)_2$ in dry benzene under nitrogen atmosphere for 3 h furnished 25-nor-friedel-7,9(11)-diene (25) which was found to be identical with the sample of 25 obtained from putrone (21). This work²² although settled the basic skeleton of putrone (21) as D:A-friedooleanane (3) but the exact position the oxo function at C-3 was not established. In later work in our laboratory²⁶, we then reduced putrone (21) with $LiAlH_4$ to furnish 23 which on acetylation followed by oxidation with SeO_2 in acetic acid yielded 3β -acetoxy-25-nor-D:A-friedoolean-7,9(11)-diene (27). This diene-acetate (27) was also prepared from the ene-acetate (20) through several steps and compound 27 thus prepared from two different compounds was found to be identical in all respects. Hence, the complete structure of putrone (21) was confirmed²⁶.

Seshadri *et al.*¹⁷ reported that putrol on oxidation with chromic acid produced putrone (21) while 21 on reduction with $NaBH_4$ gave putrol. Hence, these workers proposed putrol as the 3 α (equatorial)-hydroxy derivative (23) of putrone (21). But considering the known hydride reductions of various 3-oxofriedelanes in which the newly generated hydroxy group at C-3 always assumed the axial (β) configuration, we believed that the correct structure of putrol would be 22 and not 21 as suggested by Seshadri *et al.* It was also known that reduction of 3-oxofriedelanes with sodium and amyl alcohol always gives the thermodynamically more stable 3 α (equatorial)-alcohol. We therefore reduced putrone (21) with sodium in amyl alcohol to furnish the 3 α -hydroxy compound (23) which was found to be different from natural putrol. The acetate (28) of this 3 α -alcohol was also found to be different from putryl acetate (29) derived from natural putrol. Hence the correct structure

of putrol was shown to be **22**.

In support of the above contention, we studied the pmr spectra of a number of 3α -(equatorial) and 3β -(axial) acetoxy-D:A-friedooleananes, which revealed that the signal of the axial proton at C-3 carrying an α -acetoxy group invariably appears as a multiplet (1H) centered around δ 4.60–4.62 while the signal of the equatorial proton at C-3 carrying a β -acetoxy group exhibits a triplet (1H) in a comparatively down-field region centered around δ 4.87–4.90. Since the acetate (**29**) derived from natural putrol showed a triplet (1H) at δ 4.90, it proved beyond doubt that the correct structure of putrol is 3β -hydroxy-25-nor-D:A-friedoolean-9(11)-ene (**22**)²³.

16, R = H
18, R = OAc

19, R¹ = H; R² = OAc
20, R¹ = R² = OAc
26, R¹ = H; R² = OH

21, R = O
22, R = α -H, β -OH
23, R = α -OH, β -H
24, R = H₂
28, R = α -OAc, β -H
29, R = α -H, β -OAc

25, R = H₂
27, R = β -OAc, α -H

Chart 2

Roxburghonic acid (**30**)^{27,28}

Roxburghonic acid (**30**), C₃₀H₄₈O₃, isolated by Garg and Mitra^{13b} from the leaves of *P. roxburghii*, formed a methyl ester (**31**) on treatment with CH₂N₂ in ether. In the pmr spectrum, **31** showed the presence of six tertiary and one secondary methyl groups. It also contains a ketonic group which was reduced under normal Huang-Minlon reduction condition but the carbomethoxy group was nonreducible by LiAlH₄. The mass spectrum of **31** showed a peak at m/z 205 corresponding to the ion **32** that ruled out the possibility of existence of the carbomethoxy group at C-26, C-27, C-28, C-29 or C-30. Appearance of a peak at

m/z 153 assigned to the ion (**33**) also ruled out the possibility of the COOMe group being at C-24 and considering the nonreactivity of the ester group towards LiAlH₄, its attachment at C-23 was again ruled out. The carbomethoxy group is thus placed at C-25 and this conclusion was supported by the presence of a peak in the mass spectra at m/z 259 corresponding to the ion **34**. From the pmr spectrum of **31**, the ketonic group was believed to be at C-3 and the structure of roxburghonic acid was then proposed^{13b} as **30** although no direct correlation of **30** was made with any known D:A-friedooleanane derivative.

Recently we have established^{27,28} the proposed structure roxburghonic acid by synthesis of its methyl ester (**31**) from putranjivadione (**1**). Thus 3β -acetoxy- $7\beta,25$ -oxido-D:A-friedooleanane (**18**) previously reported by us, was oxidised with CrO₃ in acetic acid to give 3β -acetoxy-D:A-friedoolean- $7\beta \rightarrow 25$ -olide (**35**) which on alkaline hydrolysis afforded the 3β -hydroxy-olide (**36**). The lactone ring in **36** was resistant towards acid and alkali in alcoholic solutions due to steric hindrance by the axial methyls at C-5 and C-14 and the axial hydrogens at C-1 and C-12. The lactone ring was, however, opened up on treatment of **36** with lithium in boiling ethylenediamine²⁴ to give 3β -hydroxy-D:A-friedoolean-25-oic acid (**37**) which on oxidation with CrO₃ in pyridine afforded roxburghonic acid (**30**). Esterification of **30** with CH₂N₂ afforded methyl roxburghonate (**31**), found to be identical with the sample obtained from naturally occurring roxburghonic acid. The

30, R¹ = O; R² = COOH
31, R¹ = O; R² = COOMe
37, R¹ = β -OH, α -H;
R² = COOH
38, R = CHO
39, R = CH₂OH

33

34

32

35, R = OAc
36, R = OH

Chart 3

structure of roxburghonic acid was thus confirmed as 3-oxo-D:A-friedoolean-25-oic acid (30)²⁸.

Correlation of putranjivadiolone (1)⁴ with some naturally occurring 25-oxygenated D:A-friedooleananes³⁰

Although a number of 25-oxygenated D:A-friedooleananes have been isolated from different plant sources³¹⁻³⁷ but their structures were only proposed on the basis of physicochemical evidences and none of these compounds were correlated with any known D:A-friedooleanane derivative. Some of these compounds were converted to friedel-25-al (38) and friedel-25-ol (39) but their structures were also suggested on the basis of spectral data. The synthesis of these two compounds (38 and 39) from 1 was done in our laboratory in 1988 in which 1 was converted to the 7 β ,25-oxido derivative (16) and the latter on treatment with lithium in boiling ethylenediamine afforded 39 (ca 18%) and friedel-7 β -ol (7, ca 10%). The unreacted starting material 16 was recovered in ca 70% yield. Compound 39 on oxidation with CrO₃ in pyridine furnished friedel-25-al (38) and both 38 and 39 were characterised by comparison of their physical and spectral data as available in the literature^{31,32}. In the above work³⁰, the reagent lithium in ethylenediamine was used for the first time for opening of substituted tetrahydrofuran ring system to give the corresponding saturated alcohols.

Putranjivadiolone (1) has also been used in our laboratory for the study of a variety of molecular rearrangements of a number of D:A-friedooleanane derivatives under the action of various protic and aprotic reagents³⁸⁻⁴³.

References

- R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR, and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 207.
- "The Useful Plants of India", ed. S. P. AMBASTA, P.I.D., C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1986, p. 505.
- R. P. RASTOGI and B. N. MEHROTRA, "Compendium of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.D.R.I., Lucknow, and P.I.D., C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1991, Vol. 2, p. 283.
- P. SENGUPTA, A. K. CHAKRABORTY, A. M. DUFFIELD, L. J. DURHAM, and C. DJERASSI, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, 24, 1205.
- P. SENGUPTA and J. MUKHERJEE, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, 24, 6259.
- G. R. CHOPRA, A. C. JAIN and T. R. SESHADRI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1969, 38, 101.
- G. R. CHOPRA, A. C. JAIN, T. R. SESHADRI, and G. R. SOOD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 776.
- G. R. CHOPRA, A. C. JAIN, and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 401.
- G. R. CHOPRA, A. C. JAIN, and T. R. SESHADRI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1968, 37, 301.
- G. R. CHOPRA, A. C. JAIN, and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 1179.
- H. S. GARG and C. R. MITRA, *Phytochemistry*, 1968, 7, 2053.
- H. S. GARG and C. R. MITRA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1969, 232.
- (a) H. S. GARG and C. R. MITRA, *Phytochemistry*, 1971, 10, 2787; (b) *Phytochemistry*, 1971, 10, 685.
- A. K. VARSHNEY, M. AQUIL, W. RAHAMAN, M. OKIGAWA, and N. KAWANO, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, 12, 1501.
- S. RANGASWAMI and R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 189.
- R. SESHADRI and S. RANGASWAMI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 447.
- V. N. AIYAR, G. R. CHOPRA, A. C. JAIN, and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 525.
- V. HARIHARAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 830.
- V. HARIHARAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 447.
- V. HARIHARAN, *J. Res. Indian Med.*, 1974, 9, 70 and *Chem Abstr* 1976, 85, 17103.
- H. S. GARG and C. R. MITRA, *Planta Medica*, 1968, 16, 17.
- P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, and S. N. RAO, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1979, 60.
- P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, S. N. MAITI, and S. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 918.
- P. SENGUPTA and A. K. DEY, *Tetrahedron*, 1972, 28, 1307.
- P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, S. SENGUPTA, and K. G. DAS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 4197.
- P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, B. MITRA, and S. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, 28, 21.
- S. K. GHOSH, B. MITRA, and S. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, 30, 968.
- S. K. GHOSH, S. K. DATTA, and S. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1994, 33, 370.
- B. P. PRADHAN, A. HASSAN, and J. N. SHOOLERY, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, 25, 865.
- B. MITRA, M. SEN, and S. DAS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1988, 29, 6971.
- J. L. COURTNEY and R. M. GASCOIGNE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2115.
- J. L. COURTNEY, R. M. GASCOIGNE, and A. Z. SZUMER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2119.
- J. L. COURTNEY, G. G. MACDONALD, and J. S. SHANNON, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1963, 173.
- J. L. COURTNEY and W. STERN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1965, 1607.
- A. S. R. ANJANEYULU and M. N. RAO, *Phytochemistry*, 1990, 19, 1163.
- G. WEERATUNGA, V. KUMAR, and M. U. S. SUTANBAWA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, 23, 2031.
- G. WEERATUNGA, V. KUMAR, and M. U. S. SULTANBAWA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1983, 36, 1067.
- P. SENGUPTA, J. MUKHERJEE, and M. SEN, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, 27, 2473.
- P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, and U. SARKAR, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. I*, 1978, 384.
- P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, and M. BASAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 1166.
- P. SENGUPTA, M. SEN, and S. N. MAITI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, 18, 504.
- P. SENGUPTA, S. DAS, and K. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, 24, 1175.
- S. K. DUTTA, S. K. GHOSH, K. MAJUMDAR, and S. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1995, 34, 960.